

Role of Coordinators as Curriculum and Instructional Managers

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Abstract—The study sought to assess the role of subject coordinators in curriculum and instruction management of the basic education, elementary and secondary levels of Colegio de San Juan de Letran. The purpose of the study is to assess the role of subject coordinators in curriculum management to closely monitor the implementation of curriculum instruction and improve curriculum delivery. The study used the descriptive survey design. The population of the study comprised seven (7) subject coordinators and 25 faculty members of the basic education department. The measuring instruments used were survey questionnaires for teachers and for subject coordinators. Data was analyzed quantitatively and qualitatively. The study established that most subject coordinators were often times engaging in their roles on curriculum and instruction management, teaching and learning resources were available but not adequate for use, subject coordinators were discussing issues on curriculum instructions with staff during area meetings, and school motivated the staff members by delegating responsibilities to them, consulting them regularly, recognizing their achievements and appreciating their work. The study recommends that subject coordinators should improve on frequency of visiting lesson sessions, checking teachers notes or plans, inviting teachers to observe him/her teach and check students' tasks to ensure monitoring and maintain quality assurance.

Keywords— Curriculum and instruction; Educational Management; Education.

I. INTRODUCTION

Education is an essential agent in the national development of the country. Improving the quality of education, especially in the basic education level, has become the concern of all nations. The school management is directly involved in curriculum implementation and supervision. Kotirde and Yunos (2014), emphasized this by indicating that the concern for quality has been the center of the motivating forces for changes in education and achieving quality in education has increasingly become a crucial strategic improvement plans of developing countries. Achieving educational aims and providing quality basic education greatly depend on the significant role played by teachers in determining the nature of education received in schools (Gwaradzimba & Shumba, 2010). This means that the stakeholders of education need to ensure the performance tasks of teachers should be to the best of their abilities in order to offer quality education to students.

In the article written by Bilboa, Lucido, Iringan and Javier (2008), stated that a curriculum is considered the heart of any

learning institution which means that schools cannot exist without a curriculum. In its broadest sense, curriculum refers to the total learning experiences of individuals not only in school but society as well. Curriculum management plays a vital role in improving the economy of a country, provides solutions to the world's pressing conditions and problems such as environment, politics, socio-economics and other issues of poverty, climate change, and sustainable development. Integrating real- life situations and current issues will help the subject coordinators in the enhancement of the curriculum. The subject coordinators should be abreast of the current issues in the environment. Instructional management is a process of bringing about improvement in the teaching-learning process through cooperative activities and democratic relationship of persons concerned with teaching and learning which is important in achieving effective education system (Oyewole & Echinola, 2014). Likewise, Aguba (2009), stated that instructional management is concerned with student learning in the classroom and seen as a collaborative effort which involves a set of activities structured with the aim of improving the teaching and learning process. This means that the instructional management is characterized by all those activities which are undertaken to help teachers maintain and improve their effectiveness in the classroom. However, it is not designed to find faults or punish but rather, to see the teacher as a colleague and work together to enhance teaching and learning in schools.

Glickman, Gordon and Ross-Gordon (2009), also stated that instructional management is considered an important activity in the management and administration of educational institutions because it ensures the quality of educational organizations and draws together disconnected elements of instruction into whole-school actions.

Arong and Ogbadu (2010), stated that instructional management provides opportunities for schools to be effective for improving professional development of teachers to effectively manage teaching and learning processes. It could be said that the general consensus from literature is that instructional management aims at improving practice, student learning achievement, reflection and improving the overall school, and these goals could be achieved when teachers learn with and from one another according to Harrison and Killion

(2007). It is therefore, deduced that to promote quality teaching and learning in the basic education, stakeholders need to pay attention to instructional management.

A cohesive transition from instructional management to differentiated system of management in tune with growth level, personality characteristics, needs and interests, and professional commitments of teachers is needed (Sergiovanni, 2009). The TILS Tennessee Instructional Leadership Schools (2008) indicate that an effective instructional leader creates a school culture and climate based on high expectations that are conducive to the success of all learners. In order to fulfill this important role, the instructional leader should be able to do the following: develop and sustain a school culture based on ethics, diversity, equity, and collaboration, advocate, nurture and lead a culture conducive to learning; develop and sustain a safe, secure and disciplined learning environment; model and communicate self-discipline and engagement in life-long learning to staff, learner and parent; facilitate and sustain a culture and protects and maximizes learning time; and develop a leadership learn designed to share responsibilities and ownership in terms of meeting the school's learning goals.

Malik, Danish and Ushman (2010), stated that motivation significantly determines education achievements and outcomes. This implies that objectives of educational institutions can be achieved when employees are well motivated. According to Iwu, Gwija, Benedict and Tengeh (2013), motivated teachers are therefore more satisfied and this brings about higher performance than those who are less motivated.

The study of Wanzare (2012), established that instructional management practices significantly relate with motivation and concluded that the subject coordinators are expected to provide the right motivation and stimulation for staff through instructional supervisory role. They are to use supervisor-teacher friendly methods and move from the traditional method of control and authoritarianism to more cooperative and collaborative practices.

From the speeches in seminars about curriculum conducted by the Department of Education, Briones (2018), pointed out that curriculum describes the what of instruction, what is intentionally taught to students in a classroom, while instruction describes the how the curriculum is delivered. It illustrates how to effectively teach what students should know and be able to do and the opportunities to learn that actually occur in the classroom.

Instructional management today includes much deeper involvement in the core technology of teaching and learning, carries more sophisticated views of professional development, and emphasizes the use of data in decision making. The subject coordinators or curriculum leaders must be able to collect data from the performance of the learners and use the data to develop teaching and learning improvement initiatives.

Based on the revised Faculty Manual (2018), the mission-vision of Colegio de San Juan de Letran stated that there is a need to raise the awareness, standards and quality Education through programs in academics, research and community service for quality Instructional management in order to

produce responsive and responsible students who are ready for a relevant role in the world.

In the Organizational Manual of Colegio de San Juan de Letran (2018), the Area Coordinator is the Faculty Member immediately responsible for the daily operation and management of the area. The position is responsible for the attainment of the academic goals and objectives of the area. The position shall be responsible for the continued growth and enhancement of the area, including teaching, research, scholarly activities and supervision of faculty. For the detailed job descriptions, the main tasks of a subject coordinator are curriculum management, professional growth, student management, research, monitoring and public relation and linkage.

This study was based on Role Theory proposed by Goffman (1961) and later developed by Biddle (1986). The role theory is concerned with how rules, norms and expectations associated with positions held influence behavior of individuals in an organization. Roles specify what goals should be pursued, what tasks must be accomplished, and what performances are required in a given scenario or situation. Role failure takes place when individuals occupying certain positions fail to live up to the expectations of their status.

The researchers of this study sought to find out the role of subject coordinators in curriculum and instructional management where the respondents were the seven subject coordinators and twenty-five (25) teachers in the Basic Education Department. The following research questions guided the study: 1. how do subject coordinators evaluate their teachers in terms of curriculum and instruction practices, teaching and learning resources, methods of motivating staff members, and channels of communication; and 2. how do subject coordinators prepare their staff for professional growth and service training?

The study may contribute to the advancement of knowledge about the role of subject coordinators in the management of curriculum instruction. It may be of immediate benefit to the Basic Education in the formulation of future policies aimed at enhancing curriculum and instruction management. More specifically, the performance of students across standard tasks can be used by teachers to monitor progress and adapt instructional programs as needed for each student individually as stated by Deno (1985, 1986).

The study sought to find out the role of subject coordinators in curriculum and instructional management. The respondents were the subject coordinators and the teachers themselves of the Basic Education Department. The study was based on the conceptual framework below.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework of the Different Roles of Subject Coordinators as Instructional Managers

In this conceptual framework it was conceptualized that high academic achievement can be achieved by effective curriculum instructional management. The focus was on the subject coordinators, the central independent variable. Effective curriculum instruction management depended on the subject coordinators to determine the desired results.

The Role Theory is of great relevance to this study. The study sought to find out the role of the subject coordinators in curriculum management. The subject coordinator has a role to select and produce instructional materials which help the teachers to perform their duties better and improve instruction through effective leadership. It is evident that the success of every school curriculum design depend on the administration, as school manager, the subject coordinator should make teaching possible by stimulating desired changes in the professional behavior of the teachers, he or she has to provide adequate textbooks supplies and equipment. Effective instructional leadership demand that he or she must be competent teacher and should keep informed to recent development in curriculum in general and instruction supervision in particular.

According to Mojica (2018), subject coordinators' curriculum instructional management leads to effective teaching resulting into high academic achievement of students which can be measured through written work, performance tasks, and quarterly assessment. Being champions in academic and extra-curricular activities in local, national and international competitions can also be the measures for high achievements of instruction. Likewise, she emphasized in her Faculty Development Program, that curriculum instructional management includes management plans for carrying out curriculum goals, regular monitoring of teachers' professional records, and regular class supervision. The subject coordinators have a role to select and produce instructional materials which will help the teachers to perform their duties better and improve instruction through effective instructional leadership. Good education is a product of good curriculum management. This means creating and developing incentive for curriculum implementation, creating an atmosphere in which teachers can freely interact professionally, developing team work and encouraging potential leaders among the members.

II. METHODOLOGY

The study used a descriptive survey design to establish the role of Subject Coordinators in curriculum and instructional

management in the basic education of Colegio de San Juan de Letran, Manila. This study was inspired by the Role Theory by Goffman (1961). Based on this design the researcher constructed questions which helped solicit the desired information, contribute to accurate and fair interpretation of results, deeper insight and better understanding of the performance of subject coordinators in curriculum instruction management. The participants of the study were seven (7) subject coordinators and twenty-five (25) full time faculty members.

A survey instrument was used as a tool to answer the research questions presented earlier. The questionnaire consists of the background information of the participants, school management activities, learning resources, and channels of communications. Open-ended questions were used to obtain detailed information about the participants' opinions on enhancing curriculum instructional management in the department. Data analysis was then performed using qualitative and quantitative techniques. The researcher consulted and got expert judgment to enhance the validity of the instrument. After discussing, the researcher incorporated the recommendations in the final research instrument.

The questionnaires were distributed to the subject coordinators and to the teachers to be accomplished in a day. Data analysis was then performed using both quantitative and qualitative techniques.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

TABLE 1. Demographic Profile of Respondents

	Faculty n=25		Coordinators n=7	
	f	%	f	%
Age				
21 -30	7	28	0	0
31 -40	10	40	2	28.57
41 -50	5	20	1	14.28
51 -60	3	12	4	57.14
A. Professional Qualifications				
Bachelor Degree	2	8	0	0
M.A. units	19	76	2	28.57
M.A. Degree	4	16	3	42.85
Ph.D. units	0	0	2	28.57
C. Experience				
	as Classroom Teacher	n=25	as Coordinator	n=11
Number of Years	f	%	f	%
1-3 years	4	16	4	36
4-10 years	8	32	2	18
11-15 years	4	16	4	36
16-20 years	2	8	1	9
21-25 years	2	8	0	0
26-30 years	4	16	0	0
31-35 years	1	4	0	0
D. Teaching Loads and Number of Preparations				
	f	%	f	%
6 loads	12	48	0	0
6.5 or more loads	11	44	0	0
Less than 6 loads	2	8	7	100
1 to 4 preparation/s	20	80	7	100
5 or more preparations	5	20	0	0

As shown in Table 1, the respondents of the study were twenty-five (25) faculty members and seven (7) subject coordinators. Out of the twenty-five (25) faculty members, ten (10) are between thirty-one to forty (31-40) years old. There are seven (7) young ones between twenty-one to thirty (21-30) years old. And there are five (5) teachers who are in the bracket of forty-one to fifty (41-50) years old. Only three (3) teachers are between fifty-one to sixty (51-60) years old. Among the coordinators, two (2) are between thirty-one to forty (31-40) years old, only one (1) is between forty-one to fifty (41-50) years old, and four of them are between fifty to

sixty (50-60) years old. The more number of years of stay in their jobs, the more experiences they have gained.

For professional qualifications, nineteen (19) have earned M.A units, four (4) have earned their M.A. degree and only two (2) teachers have not enrolled in graduate studies. Among the subject coordinators, three (3) have earned their M.A. degree, two (2) are with M.A. units and two (2) are with doctoral units.

Thirty-two percent (32%) of the teachers have four to ten (4-10) years of experience as classroom teachers. Sixteen percent (16 %) have one to three (1-3) years, eleven to fifteen (11-15) years and twenty-six to thirty (26-30) years of experience. The rest have thirty-two percent (32%), eight percent (8%) and only one (1) with four percent (4%) thirty to thirty-five (31-35) years of experience. From the subject coordinators, sixteen percent (16%) are with one to three (1-3) years of experience and eleven to fifteen (11-15) years. Two (2) or eighteen percent (18%) coordinators have four to ten (4-10) years of experience and only one(1) or (4%) is within the bracket of thirty-one to thirty-five (31-35) years of experience.

Eighty percent (80%) of the teachers have one to four (1-4) preparations and the rest of the twenty percent (20%) of the teachers have five (5) or more preparations. Forty-eight percent of the teachers have six (6) loads. Forty-four percent (44%) have more than 6.5 loads and only eight percent (8%) have two loads due to their other positions. The subject coordinators are given only three loads and with one or two preparations only for them to give more attention to their supervisory tasks.

TABLE 2. Involvement in Management Activities as Perceived by Subject Coordinators (N=7)

Management Activities	Never		Rarely		Sometimes		Often		Always	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
1. Checks records and schemes of work	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	14.28	6	85.7
2. Visit lesson sessions classroom	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	57.14	3	42.85
3. Check student assignment	1	14.28	0	0	0	0	2	28.57	4	57.14
4. Provide adequate teaching and learning	0	0	1	14.28	0	0	2	28.57	4	57.14
5. Encourage use of academic time	0	0	0	0	1	14.28	1	14.28	1	14.28
6. Checks teachers Lesson notes	0	0	1	14.28	0	0	2	28.57	4	57.14
7. Invite teachers for model teaching	3	42.85	0	0	2	28.57	1	14.28	1	14.28
8. Identify competent teachers and assign them responsibilities	0	0	1	14.28	1	14.28	0	0	5	71.42
9. Keep records of individual staff members	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7	100

Table 2 shows the responses of the subject coordinators regarding their involvement in management activities. Eighty-five percent (85 %) of the seven subject coordinators check records and schemes of work always and fourteen percent (14%) answered often. Fifty-seven percent (57%) often visit lesson sessions or conduct classroom observations while forty-two percent (42%) always visit lesson sessions in the classrooms. Fifty-seven percent (57%) of the subject coordinators always and twenty-eight percent (28%) often check the assignment and provide adequate teaching and learning materials. Also fifty-seven percent (57%) of the subject coordinators check teachers lesson notes or lesson plans always. Seventy-one percent (71%) of the subject coordinators always encourage their subordinate on the use of academic time while fourteen percent (14 %) sometimes and often. Also seventy-one percent of the subject coordinator

identify competent teachers and assign them responsibilities. Only two coordinators fell under rarely and sometimes. All subject coordinators keep records of individual staff members.

TABLE 3. Involvement of the Subject Coordinators in Management Activities as Perceived by Faculty Members

Management Activities	Never		Rarely		Sometimes		Often		Always	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
1. Checks records and schemes of work	0	0	0	0	1	4	12	48	12	48
2. Visit lesson sessions classroom	2	8	0	0	2	8	12	48	9	36
3. Check student assignment	3	12	1	4	4	16	4	16	13	52
4. Provide adequate teaching and learning	0	0	0	0	1	4	11	44	13	52
5. Encourage use of academic time	0	0	0	0	3	12	4	16	18	72
6. Checks teachers Lesson notes	5	20	0	0	5	20	8	32	7	28
7. Invite teachers for model teaching	9	36	7	28	3	12	3	12	3	12
8. Identify competent teachers and assign them responsibilities	2	8	2	8	7	28	7	28	7	28
9. Keep records of individual staff members	3	12	0	0	0	0	9	36	13	52

From the responses of the faculty members regarding the involvement of the subject coordinators in management activities, four percent (4%) answered sometimes, forty-eight percent (48%) often and always check records and schemes of work. Although the subject coordinators are required to visit lesson sessions in the classrooms, eight percent (8%) answered never and sometimes, while forty-eight percent (48%) often and twenty-five percent (25%) always. Twenty-five percent (25%) of the subject coordinators check student assignments and provide adequate teaching and learning materials.

Twenty-eight percent (28%) always check teachers lesson notes or lesson plans and identify competent teachers and assign responsibilities. Three percent (3%) believed that the subject coordinators never keep records of individual staff members, thirty-six percent (35%) often and fifty-two percent (52%) always.

TABLE 4. Methods used by Subject Coordinators in Evaluating Teachers' Performance as Perceived by Teachers

Methods used for motivating Teachers' performance	Never		Rarely		Sometimes		Often		Always	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
1. Attend in-service training	0	0	0	0	4	16	10	40	11	44
2. Guide teachers on weak areas	2	8	1	4	7	28	7	28	8	32
3. Organize meetings and involve teachers in making school programs	2	8	0	0	2	8	11	44	10	40
4. Periodical inspection of Coverage of teaching syllabus	1	4	1	4	3	12	9	36	11	44
5. Consult head of the department on teachers' areas that require improvement in teaching and learning	0	0	0	0	5	20	7	28	13	52
6. Teacher's work is appreciated	0	0	0	0	5	20	7	28	13	52
7. Achievement recognized	2	8	0	0	5	20	5	20	14	56
8. Regular consultation of teachers	2	8	0	0	5	20	10	40	8	32
9. Sympathize with while in problems	0	0	1	4	5	20	5	20	14	56

Table 4 shows the teachers responses on the methods used by the subject coordinators in evaluating the performance of the teachers. Forty-four percent (44%) of the teachers are provided with in-service training. Thirty-two percent (32%) are always guided on weak areas while eight percent (8%) are never guided. The subject coordinators always organize meetings (44%). They also do periodical inspections of the coverage of syllabus always (40%). According to the teachers (44%), the subject coordinators consult the head of the department on teachers' areas that require improvement in

teaching and learning. Fifty-six percent (52%) of the teachers said, the coordinators show appreciation of their works and sympathize with them (56%) while they are in problems.

TABLE 5. Methods Used for Motivating Teachers' Performance as Perceived by Subject Coordinators

Methods used for motivating Teachers' performance	Never		Rarely		Sometimes		Often		Always	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
1. Attend in-service training	5	17	0	0	1	14.2	1	14.2	0	0
2. Guide teachers on weak areas	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	14.2	6	85.7
3. Organize meetings and involve teachers in making school programs	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	85.7	2	28.5
4. Periodical inspection of Coverage of teaching syllabus	0	0	1	14.2	1	14.2	0	0	6	85.7
5. Consult head of the department on teachers' areas that require improvement in teaching and learning	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	28.5	2	28.5
6. Teacher's work is appreciated	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	14.2	6	85.7
7. Achievements recognized	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	14.2	6	85.7
8. Regular consultation of teachers	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	28.5	5	71.4
9. Sympathize with while in problems	0	0	0	0	1	14.2	2	28.5	2	28.5

According to the subject coordinators (14%), teachers attend in-service training often and seventy-one percent (71%) answered never. Almost all subject coordinators (85%) guide their teachers on weak areas and do periodical inspection of coverage of teaching syllabus as well as appreciate teachers' work and recognize their achievement. The subject coordinators organize meetings and involve teachers in making decisions (57%) often. Seventy-one percent (71%) of the subject coordinators have regular consultation of teachers always. Above forty-two percent (42%) of the subject coordinators sympathize with their teachers while in problems, likewise consult the head of the department on areas that require improvement in teaching and learning.

In-service training helps teachers to acquire new knowledge and new skills for the purpose of empowerment, consolidation and better understanding of existing curriculum, updating teachers in new curriculum, and identified problems existing in the curriculum. As a way of motivating staff members, the researcher sought to establish whether the teacher and the subject coordinators have ever attended any in-service training. The result reviewed shows that, all teachers and subject coordinators have attended in-service training course. The courses that were covered included: keeping and updating schemes of work, teaching methodology, preparation of lesson plans, progressive records and development of teaching and learning resources. Through an informal interview with one subject coordinator, the researcher sought to determine how subject coordinators initiated and stimulated incentives to the teachers. In response, the subject coordinator reported that they motivated the teachers through giving them incentives for good performance, taking them out for lunch, commending them orally and through notes of appreciation.

Table 6 shows that 100% teaching and learning resources are available but not adequate. Ninety-two percent (92%) of the teacher respondents answered yes on the availability of laboratory and equipment and only eight percent (8%) answered no. All subject coordinators believed that all learning and teaching resources are available but not all are

adequate. Eighty-five percent (85%) of the subject coordinators answered yes for the availability of the laboratory equipment and fourteen percent (14%) inadequate.

TABLE 6. Availability and Adequacy of Teaching and Learning Resources as Perceived by Teachers and Subject Coordinators

	Teachers (n=25)				Subject Coordinator (n=7)			
	Availability		Adequacy		Sometimes		Often	
	YES	NO	YES	NO	YES	NO	YES	NO
1. Teaching aids	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
2. Library	24	96	1	4	7	100	0	0
3. Textbooks	25	100	0	0	7	100	0	0
4. Classrooms	25	100	0	0	7	100	0	0
5. Classroom furniture areas that require	25	100	0	0	7	100	0	0
6. Laboratory	22	88	3	12	6	85.7	1	14.28
7. Laboratory equipment	23	92	2	8	7	100	0	0
8. TV Screen/ technology	25	100	0	0	7	100	0	0
9. Other materials	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

TABLE 7. Frequency of Staff Meetings and Display of Timetable for Examinations as Perceived by Teachers and Subject Coordinator

	Faculty (n=25)				Subject Coordinators (n=7)			
	Time table for Exams		Staff Meetings		Time table for Exams		Staff Meetings	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
1. Monthly	3	12	5	20	0	0	1	14.28
2. Quarterly	22	88	20	80	7	100	3	42.85
3. Semestral	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
4. Once a year	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

It can be seen in Table 7 that eighty-eight percent (88%) of the faculty and 100% of the subject coordinators answered that the timetable for examinations are displayed quarterly, likewise, staff meetings are also held quarterly, for some every semester, and one (1) every month.

TABLE 8. Communication Channels used to Perceived by Teachers and Subject Coordinators

	Faculty (n=15)		Subject Coordinators (n=7)	
	f	%	f	%
1. Memoranda	22	88	7	100
2. Notice board	21	84	4	57.14
3. School Assembly	18	72	2	28.57
4. Staff Meetings	24	96	6	85.71

Table 8 illustrates that according to teachers (88%) and subject coordinators (100%) most of the subject coordinators used memoranda to communicate information on curriculum implementation. Ninety-six percent (96%) of the teachers and eighty-five percent of the subject coordinators answered that staff meetings are called to discuss issues on curriculum and instructions. School assemblies (72%) are also used as communication according to the teachers and 28% according to the subject coordinators. To verify the responses of the teachers and subject coordinators on forums used by the subject coordinators to communicate information, the researcher asked the coordinators. In response, they reported that they communicated information on curriculum and instruction during staff meetings and during the assemblies.

The study sought to assess the role of the subject coordinators in curriculum and instruction management of the basic education, elementary and secondary levels of Colegio de San Juan de Letran. The study focused on the evaluation strategies of subject coordinators to their teachers, the curriculum support for learning and teaching resources by the subject coordinators, the motivational strategies of subject coordinator to their staff, and the channels of communication between subject coordinators and teachers.

Evaluation Strategies of Subject Coordinators to their Teachers

The evaluation of teachers based on their contribution they make to the learning of their students is one of the tasks of subject coordinators. The results of evaluation can be used to help guide resources to where they are needed most, to identify teachers' strengths and weaknesses, and to put a spotlight on the critical role of teachers in learning.

Majority of the subject coordinators reported that they often organized meetings and involved the teachers in making school programs (57.1%). A significant proportion of them also indicated that they always engaged in periodical inspection of coverage of teaching syllabus (85.7%) whereas 100% indicated that they always keep written records of individual performance. This shows that most of the subject coordinators were frequently engaging in the three aspects: evaluation of teachers, curriculum support for learning, and teaching resources. However, half of the portion confirmed that the subject coordinators sympathize with teachers while in problems (42.8%) and sometimes only for one coordinator (14.2%). According to the job description of subject coordinators, the organization and control of staff, teaching and non-teaching are all part of the head's duty as the immediate supervisor of the department. In particular, she or he must check the teaching standards by reference to scheme of work, lesson notes, and record of work, students' exercise books and also the actual visit to classrooms to see the individual teacher teach. This means that effective and efficient running of the school depends on the subject coordinator's instructional management role. Subject coordinators must schedule, assign work, coordinate and oversee performance and make sure that work is done in time.

The purpose of teacher evaluation according to Mojica (2018) is to help teachers improve their teaching performance, identify training needs and get useful feedback which intern improves the institutions. Mojica asserted that subject coordinators are expected to closely monitor the performance of teachers, ensure that the right teachers are teaching the right subject, and offer professional advice through mentoring. Subject coordinators must be ready to incorporate issues and ideas.

According to 48% of teachers, subject coordinators often and always check records and schemes of work, and (72%) always encourage effective use of academic time. However, 36% of teachers reported that the subject coordinators never invited teachers to observe them when teaching. This was an indication that most of the teachers rarely or never engaged in evaluation of teachers' performance in classrooms. Based on the findings, it emerges that most of the subject coordinators partially engaged in curriculum and instruction practices. The quality of leadership makes the difference between the success and failure of a school. For highly effective schools, it is the subject coordinator who set the pace, leading and motivating students and staff to perform to their highest potential.

Regarding classroom observation, the researchers noted that the subject coordinators often or always visited classrooms to observe individual teacher when teaching. According to Villena (2018), the man responsible for crafting

the tool for classroom observation, that classroom observation appears to work best if set in a cycle of preparation, observation and feedback, hence, the need for the coordinator and the teacher to work hand in hand before and even after observation process.

Curriculum Support for Learning and Teaching Resources by the Subject Coordinators

According to Right (2008), the quality of curriculum implementation in a school is closely related to the nature and quality of resources available and how they are used. Curriculum support materials stimulates learners' imagination and enhances memory of what is learned. All (100%) teachers who participated in the study reported that the following resources were available in the department: teachers, teaching aids, textbooks, classrooms, class furniture, laboratory and equipment, TV screen and technology materials. On the other hand, resources and equipment are inadequate respectively. The result implies that the teaching and learning resources were available but not adequate. This affect effective implementation of the curriculum which is a result of affected students' performance. There can be no effective supervision of instruction without adequate instructional materials. Ayoo (2002), stated that the presence or absence of school facilities distinguished between high and low achieving schools. All (100%) subject coordinators responded similarly, however, despite of most subject coordinators confirming that teaching and learning resources were available, most of them indicated not adequate. The most adequate resources are laboratory, laboratory equipment (14.28%), and technology materials which was not rated although available and adequate. The subject coordinator has the role to select and produce instructional materials which help the teachers to perform their duties better and improve instruction through effective leadership.

Motivational Strategies of Subject Coordinator to their Staff

Motivation is a very important aspect in the operations of any organization where results are valued. In a school, it is not only important to students but also the staff members, whether directly or indirectly. It is important that instructional supervisors be well grouped in the psychology of motivation. Motivation according to D'Souza (2003) involves ensuring an open organizational climate, which is supportive, considerate, provides satisfaction and is open to change.

The study findings revealed that 28% of the teachers indicated that the subject coordinators motivated them through delegating responsibilities and 58% said that their works were appreciated respectively. This was an indication that at least half of the proportion of teachers who participated in the study felt motivated while in school. Teachers feel motivated when they have a feeling of acceptance and inclusion, opportunity for personal growth, recognition of achievement, an awareness of being needed and an opportunity to influence events. Similarly, Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD 2009) review, found out that meaningful teacher evaluation involves accurate appraisal of the effectiveness of teaching, its strengths and areas for development, followed by feedback, coaching, support and

opportunity for professional development. It is also important to celebrate, recognize and reward the work of teachers. The results review also shows that majority of teachers reports that appraisal and feedback they receive, is beneficial, fair and helpful for their development as teachers.

Channels of Communication between Subject Coordinators and Teachers

An effective communication system establishes the relationships between and among teachers, non-teaching staff and students within the school. The role of the subject coordinator, can only be realized by an established comprehensive system of communication. Communication is essentially a bridge of understanding between people in any school according to Garrett (2009).

According to teachers (96%), most subject coordinators used staff meetings to communicate information about curriculum implementation. According to the subject coordinators (100%) they used memoranda more than the staff meetings. This was an indication that both staff meetings and memoranda are utilized to discuss issues on curriculum and instruction. Notice boards are utilized for urgent memos from the department head. The larger the school, the more imperative it is to make sure that changes in routine are notified through the proper channel. For the subject coordinators (28%), school assemblies are used for oral communications, while written communications can be done through reports, internal memo, and newsletter.

Further verifications were done to validate the quantitative data such as interview and focused discussion. From the discussion the following themes were formed. According to the subject coordinators, if the teacher weakness is about classroom management, mentoring assisting the teacher to improve will help a lot. From the teachers' point of view the use of clinical supervision may help the teacher to overcome the weaknesses. The teacher and the subject coordinator should agree on what to give emphasis during classroom observation

Mentoring is an important aspect of supervision to improve curriculum and instruction, and to improve the teaching strategies according to the subject coordinators. Mentoring is an ideal way of inspiring a teacher to become better in his instructional effectiveness especially for the new teachers to allow them to flourish in the manner they think best while offering some traditional wisdom or communication and sense of priorities. Teachers mention that mentoring new teachers can develop harmonious relationship and adjustment to the system of the school. Mentoring new teachers can also inspire the teacher to do his best.

For the improvement of curriculum and instruction management in the basic education department, the subject coordinators mentioned the review of the syllabi and its alignment to the lessons taught by the teacher in each area, to have a bank of instructional materials, to re-orient the stakeholders on their responsibilities and peer demonstration of the best teachers. In order to improve the curriculum and instruction management in the basic education, proactive meetings should be practiced and the yearly evaluation on the

needs of the teachers. Through proactive meetings and evaluation of the needs of teachers, topics for training and the type of seminars can easily be identified.

For the ways used subject coordinators to evaluate teachers, the study established that they often organized meetings and involved teacher in making school programs. A significant proportion of them indicated that they always engaged in periodical inspection of coverage of teaching syllabus and that they always keep written records of individual performance. This shows that most of the subject coordinators were engaging in their supervisory roles. The study also revealed that the subject coordinators and teachers responses in curriculum and instruction practices are almost the same. According to teachers most of the subject coordinators often engaged in evaluation of teachers' performance in classroom while the subject coordinators reported that the most subject coordinators engaged in curriculum practices. Putting more emphasis on instructional supervision practices, teachers would improve their academic performance. The provision of learning resources by the subject coordinators will ensure effective teaching and learning.

Subject coordinators can inspire their teachers by delegating responsibilities and consulting them regularly, appreciating their work, and giving recognition for an outstanding work.

On the channels of communication between subject coordinators and the teachers, staff meetings and memoranda are useful means to communicate information in curriculum implementation.

IV. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Based on the findings the study concludes that subject coordinators should put more emphasis on curriculum instructional supervision practices which would translate to improvement in academic performance. Subject coordinators should assist their teachers in preparing instructional materials and learning resources for an effective curriculum. Delegating responsibilities and work appreciation can motivate teachers to work harmoniously with one another. For improvement of curriculum and instructional management, subject coordinators should improve on: frequency on visiting lesson sessions, checking teachers' lesson notes, inviting teachers to observe him/her teach and checking students assignments or tasks to ensure regular marking takes place.

On the issue of curriculum support and learning resources, inadequate resources should be given much attention for it will affect the performance in curriculum and instruction evaluation. Subject coordinators and school head should develop and maintain a system of communication that provide for an upward flow to benefit decision making, downward flow to benefit the implementation of policy, and horizontal flow to facilitate coordination of all teachers and other departments. Another study should be carried out to find out if parental factors and community factors influence subject coordinators role in management of curriculum and instruction in the school. Another study should be carried out to find out how instructional supervision affects student discipline.

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